

The Relationship between Customer Relationship Management and Customer Satisfaction with the Expected Value of the Consumer Audio and Video Products Samsung in Kerman.

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Abstract:

At present, the real mission of the organization, understanding the needs and demands of the customers and provide solutions that will be in customer satisfaction. Naturally, the need to establish a strategy to manage these relationships will be felt. Therefore, one of the factors considered by managers, customer relationship management. The purpose of this paper is to investigate the relationship between customer relationship management and customer satisfaction is the expected value of the consumer audio and video products Samsung in Kerman.

Keywords: Customer, Customer Relationship, customer satisfaction, the expected value of customer, Samsung

Introduction:

One of the environmental factors and affecting on organization is customers an organization. Experts in management, customer satisfaction is considered the most important responsibilities of management organizations and Permanent and stable top management commitment to customer satisfaction are prerequisites to success. Today, managers are well aware that their success in achieving the major goals of the organization depends on the satisfaction of our customers. For this reason, customer relationship management, business strategy is to attract, retain and promote customer-focused. One of the issues that today's attracting and keeping customers is a priority for many. And important factors in the success of the company is customer value. Customers can choose good or service that they believe will provide the most value.

Theoretical Research:

Companies to attract new customers and bargain with them, have been trying to retain current customers and create a permanent relationship with them. In other words, they have found that the loss of a customer, the greater the loss of a sale item and It means losing the entire stream of purchases that the customer would have in their lifetime or Or time period that the buyer was the company's products do. So, in an effort to preserve customer economically affordable and is regarded companies. Customer satisfaction, emotional response (affective) or a state of mutual understanding and recognition. Dissatisfaction or lack of customer satisfaction, is a condition in which one of the factors causing dissatisfaction enough on his perception of the quality of products or services purchased affects. (Pratn, 2004:383)

Organizations in the new business processes and gain customer satisfaction at the critical position is allocated to organizational goals and Senior managers

are well aware that their success in achieving the major goals of the organization depends on the satisfaction of our customers. On the other hand, can not be said that all customers are equally involved in the success of the organization. Therefore, the key to customer satisfaction, will be more sensitive. Thus, organization need a system to attract and retain customers is to design and implement. System, which can well manage customer relationships and the organization. Today, these systems are known as customer relationship management systems. (Khosravi, 1390:2)

The issue of how to communicate with their customers and maintain long term relationship satisfaction, durability and stability of the major issues affecting their companies are more competitive and profitable. Therefore, in the present circumstances, the real mission of the organization understands the needs and demands of customers and deliver solutions that will be in customers satisfaction. (Teo Randić, 2002:312)

Managing demand means managing customers. Demand, there are usually two groups: new customers and old customers. Traditional marketing in theory and practice, the emphasis has always been on attracting new customers and sales. But today, the emphasis has changed. Management, in addition to strategies for attracting new customers and deal with them in doing has aimed to retain current customers and permanent relationship with them to bring there. (Kotler and Armstrong, 1999:28)

In the past, companies with a growing economy and markets are growing very fast, they could the method of "leaky Aquariids"s make Marketing. The purpose of growing markets, ever refer new customers. Aquarius Marketing companies could fill with new customers and not have to worry about losing old customers due to a hole in the Aquariids. But now companies are facing new realities of marketing. Combined population is constantly changing, Economy grows very slow pace, Competing firms are much more

complex, and many industries are faced with excess capacity. Because of these factors can be found in lots of new customers. Now companies to gain a larger share of the market is stable or declining to fight. Therefore, the cost of attracting new customers are rising. In fact, the cost of attracting new customers, retaining current customers is five times the cost. (Kotler and Armstrong, 1999:28)

Customer relationship management in general, the design process is organized around customers' needs and demands of the customer so that the main be considered in any organizational decisions. The customer relationship management, the focus is on the customer brief. the goal of creating a customer-focused organization, increasing the value of the customer and the customer relationship is on its side. The value of the organization of improvement in customer retention and increase revenue, but has greater performance and control costs. (Brown, 2000:258)

Second Sapynt company, customer relationship management has been defined as: "Customer Relationship Management is a customer-oriented organizational model that a structured customer data to create a customized strategy uses. This strategy consistently through all channels of communication with the customer is running. The value of this strategy, customer retention and increase revenue, but has greater performance and control costs. (Sapynt, 2004).

One of the issues that today's attracting and keeping customers is a priority of many important factors in the success of the company is considered customer value. Customers can choose good or service that they believe will provide the most value. Whether the goods or services supplied or not the expected value can be given to customer satisfaction and Behaviors observed in purchasing again. Customer buys goods from a company that believes will provide the greatest value to him. The purpose of providing the highest value to the customer, which is the difference between total customer value and total cost that will be paid there. (Kotler and Armstrong, 1999:864)

"Warren Keegan 2002" Marketing Science experts believe that only focusing resources on opportunities and create value for our customers sustainable competitive advantage that can be achieved and strong support for the continued existence of the organization's leadership in the arena of competition where it can find. the best approach to maintaining our customers, creating great customer satisfaction and attention to for what he considered to be the result of his loyalty to the company is stronger. (haghgooei, 1389:81)

Value for the customer, is based on three principles: 1 - good quality 2 - Quality of service 3 - price based on the value, obviously, the two principles, quality products and quality service, backed by a third of the price based on value and if there is coordination between these three principles, the customer value is maximized. It must be understood that high quality products without having the proper service, the maximum value to the customer does not, as the service quality with inferior goods is unable to create maximum value for customer, As the service quality with inferior goods is unable to create maximum value for customers, have must strive to strike a balance between product quality and service quality, and price is based on values established. (Teo Randić, 2002:312)

Consumers, so they make judgments about the value of the products offered, to buys (Based on the judgments, decisions are purchasing). Buying customer satisfaction, product performance will depend, of course, given the expectation that the buyer of the product. The buyer may experience different degrees of satisfaction. If the product meets customer expectations, in that case, the consumer is satisfied. If performance exceeds expectations, the buyer is too complacent and take great pleasure from his work. (Kotler and Armstrong, 1999:866)

Unfortunately, dissatisfied customers, not only then, will not buy goods, but with the speed, the image of your company in their mind and others are flawed. The results of the research in this field has been done indicates that if a customer is dissatisfied, four times more than a satisfied customer of the company to complain about products, promotions will negatively. Conversely, a company with unhappy people cope and solve their problems quickly adds loyalty rate and the image customers of the company in their mind quickly improves. (Kotler and Armstrong, 1999:245)

One of the main reasons that organizations use customer relationship management applications to acquire, retain long-term customers and they are valued. Customer relationship management applications can be used to support the entire customer-focused processes in organizations of any size and grade, including marketing, sales and customer service using. Today, in order to maintain competitive strength, all organizations are looking for ways to maintain and expand the collection of customer information during marketing, sales and after-sales service are rely on customer relationship management. (Conference on Electronic Money, 1383)

Unlike classic marketing theory, the art of attracting new customers and stressed its focus on transactions to form relationships with others, with the intensification

of competition between corporations, the customer access to products and services and increasing customer power in today's competitive world, companies no longer need to follow to attract new customers but also retain previous customers and establish strong relations with them should also be considered. today's world full of change and transformation. Changes in technology, changes in the data, change the people's demands, changes in consumer and changes in global markets. But more importantly, the changes in the business, changes in the values supplied to the purchaser has been identified as a major factor in the success of existing organizations and leading organizations in every industry owes its success to the ability to supply and deliver more value to customers than their competitors to know. (haghgooei, 1389:81)

Of the most fundamental challenges in the current competitive world of business there, to attract and keep customers, increase customer loyalty and customer profitability. Successful transition of these challenges, the role of customer relationship management, highlighted the need to establish that the organization is more serious. (Vakilifard and others, 1378:71)

The goal of customer relationship management, creating a synergy between the activities of sales, marketing and after-sales services within an organization to detect and retain customers. These synergies through the exchange of information, especially among customers and various parts of the organization occurs. . (Vakilifard and others, 1378:72)

Customer Relationship Management, the idea is that customers have different demands and needs of different groups, had a different approach. Thus, customer relationship management, before the sale and marketing of their product arises because the company should be able to fit the individual needs of customers. Successful companies, customers are involved in the development of their products. Customer focus, usually means that the needs of customers in the market (average consumers) should be considered. But for effective marketing, company should continuously with individual customers can interact. One of the main benefits that customer relationship management customer loyalty and thus increase profitability. (Feizi et al, 1387:108)

In the highly competitive, customer-orientation and inattention to the demands and expectations of customers, causing death and destruction to the organization. Most markets are highly competitive and organizations to continue to produce high quality goods and services are needed, which leads to customer satisfaction and therefore loyalty becomes.

To achieve customer satisfaction, the main target firms. (khodadad Hosseini, 1383:48)

Due to the increasing attention to customer satisfaction measurement, the results are positive. Some of these consequences include: loyalty, recommend to others, reduced price sensitivity, reduce the loss of customers, increase market share, reduce costs, increase profitability and increase shareholder value. . (khodadad Hosseini, 1383:51)

Consumers are faced with a wide variety of goods and services for their decisions, assumptions or interpretations based on the type of quality, value and service they have. Companies are compelled determinants of customer value and satisfaction to understand him. Value provided to the customer is the difference between total customer value and total cost of which is borne by the customer. Customers usually will choose items that maximize the value provided to them. Customer satisfaction when it comes to the performance of the company to meet customer expectations. In this regard, customer relationship management, maintenance or storage of encryption keys, customers. (Kotler and Armstrong, 1999:900)

At present, the real mission of the organization, understanding the needs and demands of customers and deliver solutions that will be in customer satisfaction. Naturally, the need to establish a strategy to manage these relationships well be felt. Therefore, one of the subjects for managers, customer relationship management. The main reasons include: increased competition, the development of e-commerce, the top concern of information systems, the need for accurate information and special analysis can be performed. It is clear that whatever the level of customer satisfaction, are less likely to repurchase the Company will be reduced. Several studies have shown that high levels of customer satisfaction and high customer retention rates, together with the profitability of the company, have many dependencies. Also, according to this study, it has been found that the cost, time and resources necessary to attract a new customer, existing customer retention values are multiplied. Due to increasing customer demand and tougher competition, achieving high customer satisfaction, a necessary condition for survival. (Russell Voviner, 2001:3)

Therefore, the decision of firms, in particular in the different market segments and individual customers, establish a relationship, so that the amplitude of the fundamental relationship, to full participation continues and customer satisfaction to be able to attract the best kind is of particular importance. And because a research study can be applied in electronics and telecommunications, as well as industries that have a large obsession, such as Iran Khodro be used.

Also, to improve the quality of the relationship with the customer, the model used in this project can also be

used in other industries. Therefore in this research:

According to the model, Amiri and Moradi (1387) variables to identify customer needs, flexibility in service delivery, customer-centric, Understanding of customer and employee and customer loyalty, customer relationship management process as aspects of customer relationship management is used. According to the model of the Havington and navman (2003) of the variable product quality, service quality, customer and supplier relationship quality, image and price is used as the dimensions of customer satisfaction. According to the model, Wang and others (2004) of variables, functional value, emotional value, social value and worth missing the point of view of the customer, is used.

Conceptual model research:

Research hypothesis:

The main hypotheses:

1 - between the customer relationship management and customer satisfaction in between buyers of audio and video products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

2 - between customer satisfaction and customer value acceptable in between buyers of audio and video products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

3 - between the customer relationship management and customer value acceptable in between buyers of audio and video products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

sub hypotheses:

1 - between the identification of customer needs and customer satisfaction in between buyers of audio and video products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

2 - between customer understanding and customer satisfaction in between buyers of audio and video products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

3 - between the flexible of services and customer satisfaction in between buyers of audio and video products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

4 - Between customer orientation and customer satisfaction in between buyers of audio and video products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

5 - Between customer loyalty to customer relationship management and customer satisfaction in between buyers of audio and video products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

6 - Between product quality and customer value acceptable in between buyers of audio and video products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

7 - Between service quality and customer value acceptable in between buyers of audio and video products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

8 - Between The quality of the relationship between customer and supplier and customer value acceptable in between buyers of audio and video products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

9 - Between the image and customer value acceptable in between buyers of audio and video products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

10 - Between the price and customer value acceptable in between buyers of audio and video products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

11 - Between the identification of customer needs and customer value acceptable in between buyers of audio and video products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

12 - Between customer understanding and customer value acceptable in between buyers of audio and video products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

13 - Between the flexible of services and customer value acceptable in between buyers of audio and video products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

14 - Between customer orientation and customer value acceptable in between buyers of audio and video products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

15 - Between customer loyalty to customer relationship management and customer value acceptable in between buyers of audio and video products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

Materials and Methods of Research:

The present study sought to presence or absence of a relationship between variables, therefore, research methods is descriptive correlation is. Also, the expected results, it can be used in institutions. Based on objective, will be

classified as applied research. The method, field research has been done. In the present study, data collection, fieldwork and library methods will be used. In the field using three questionnaires will be used by the researcher, and validity. Questionnaire "A" consists of 45 questions, which will measure the dimensions of customer relationship management, Questionnaire "B" contains questions that will examine the status of customer satisfaction, Questionnaire "C", which includes 25 questions that measure customer value dimensions are acceptable. The scale of measurement options, 5-point scale, the Likert. The library method of taking notes as data collection will be used.

Statistical community research:

Statistical community, including all audio and video products Samsung buyers that have bought seven agencies are active in the city of Kerman, According to the Cochran formula, 201 cases, were selected as the sample size. Sampling methods used in research, sampling - stratified proportional sample size. Finally, data collected by SPSS software, using descriptive statistics, including frequency tables and graphs and statistics, Kendall and Spearman tests, are analyzed.

The main hypothesis 1:

Between the customer relationship management and customer satisfaction in between buyers of audio and video products products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

type relate	Relate	Number	Significance (p value)	The correlation coefficient	Statistics of solidarity
Direct	Yes	201	<0/001**	0/465	Pearson
Direct	yes	201	<0/001**	0/601	Spearman

Based on the results of the correlation test, Pearson correlation coefficient equal to 0/645 and Spearman correlation coefficients equal to 0/601, which is indicative of the customer relationship management and customer satisfaction in consumer audio and video products Samsung in Kerman , there is a significant relationship(p<0/05) Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the relationship between these two variables is direct. Therefore, the first main hypothesis of the research is approved. This means that changes in the rate of customer relationship management, customer satisfaction has resulted in changes to the positive (increasing) sails. This means that the increase in customer relationship management and increase customer satisfaction, and vice versa with positive tests, Pearson and Spearman coefficients, due to the increase of this relationship.

The main hypothesis 2:

Between customer satisfaction and customer value acceptable in between buyers of audio and video products products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

type relate	Relate	Number	Significance (p value)	The correlation coefficient	Statistics of solidarity
Direct	Yes	201	<0/001**	0/822	Pearson
Direct	yes	201	<0/001**	0/763	Spearman

Based on the results of the correlation test, Pearson correlation coefficient equal to 0/822 and Spearman correlation coefficients equal to 0/763, which is indicative of the customer satisfaction and customer value acceptable in

consumer audio and video products Samsung in Kerman , there is a significant relationship($p < 0/05$) Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the relationship between these two variables is direct. Therefore, the first main hypothesis of the research is approved. This means that changes in the rate of customer satisfaction, customer value acceptable has resulted in changes to the positive (increasing) sails. This means that the increase in customer satisfaction and increase customer value acceptable, and vice versa with positive tests, Pearson and Spearman coefficients, due to the increase of this relationship.

The main hypothesis 3:

Between the customer relationship management and customer value acceptable in between buyers of audio and video products products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

type relate	Relate	Number	Significance (p value)	The correlation coefficient	Statistics of solidarity
Direct	Yes	201	<0/001**	0/794	Pearson
Direct	yes	201	<0/001**	0/776	Spearman

Based on the results of the correlation test, Pearson correlation coefficient equal to 0/794 and Spearman correlation coefficients equal to 0/766, which is indicative of the customer relationship management and customer value acceptable in consumer audio and video products Samsung in Kerman , there is a significant relationship($p < 0/05$) Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the relationship between these two variables is direct. Therefore, the first main hypothesis of the research is approved. This means that changes in the rate of customer relationship management, customer value acceptable has resulted in changes to the positive (increasing) sails. This means that the increase in customer relationship management and increase customer value acceptable, and vice versa with positive tests, Pearson and Spearman coefficients, due to the increase of this relationship.

Sub hypotheses 1-1:

Between the identification of customer needs and customer satisfaction in between buyers of audio and video products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

type relate	Relate	Number	Significance (p value)	The correlation coefficient	Statistics of solidarity
Direct	Yes	201	<0/001**	0/452	Pearson
Direct	yes	201	<0/001**	0/415	Spearman

Based on the results of the correlation test, Pearson correlation coefficient equal to 0/452 and Spearman correlation coefficients equal to 0/415, which is indicative of the identification of customer needs and customer satisfaction in consumer audio and video products Samsung in Kerman , there is a significant relationship($p < 0/05$) Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the relationship between these two variables is direct. Therefore, the first main hypothesis of the research is approved. This means that changes in the rate of identification of customer needs, customer satisfaction has resulted in changes to the positive (increasing) sails. This means that the increase in identification of customer needs and increase customer satisfaction, and vice versa with positive tests, Pearson and Spearman coefficients, due to the increase of this relationship.

Sub hypotheses 1-2:

Between customer understanding and customer satisfaction in between buyers of audio and video products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

type relate	Relate	Number	Significance (p value)	The correlation coefficient	Statistics of solidarity
Direct	Yes	201	<0/001**	0/497	Pearson
Direct	yes	201	<0/001**	0/451	Spearman

Based on the results of the correlation test, Pearson correlation coefficient equal to 0/497 and Spearman correlation coefficients equal to 0/451, which is indicative of the customer understanding and customer satisfaction in consumer audio and video products Samsung in Kerman , there is a significant relationship($p < 0/05$) Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the relationship between these two variables is direct. Therefore, the first main hypothesis of the research is approved. This means that changes in the rate of customer understanding, customer satisfaction has resulted in changes to the positive (increasing) sails. This means that the increase in customer understanding and increase customer satisfaction, and vice versa with positive tests, Pearson and Spearman coefficients, due to the increase of this relationship.

Sub hypotheses 1-3:

Between the flexible of services and customer satisfaction in between buyers of audio and video products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

type relate	Relate	Number	Significance (p value)	The correlation coefficient	Statistics of solidarity
Direct	Yes	201	<0/001**	0/489	Pearson
Direct	yes	201	<0/001**	0/463	Spearman

Based on the results of the correlation test, Pearson correlation coefficient equal to 0/489 and Spearman correlation coefficients equal to 0/463, which is indicative of the the flexible of services and customer satisfaction in consumer audio and video products Samsung in Kerman , there is a significant relationship($p < 0/05$) Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the relationship between these two variables is direct. Therefore, the first main hypothesis of the research is approved. This means that changes in the rate of the flexible of services, customer satisfaction has resulted in changes to the positive (increasing) sails. This means that the increase in the flexible of services and increase customer satisfaction, and vice versa with positive tests, Pearson and Spearman coefficients, due to the increase of this relationship.

Sub hypotheses 1-4:

Between customer orientation and customer satisfaction in between buyers of audio and video products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

type relate	Relate	Number	Significance (p value)	The correlation coefficient	Statistics of solidarity
Direct	Yes	201	<0/001**	0/617	Pearson
Direct	Yes	201	<0/001**	0/617	Spearman

Based on the results of the correlation test, Pearson correlation coefficient equal to 0/617 and Spearman correlation coefficients equal to 0/617, which is indicative of the customer orientation and customer satisfaction in consumer audio and video products Samsung in Kerman , there is a significant relationship(p<0/05) Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the relationship between these two variables is direct. Therefore, the first main hypothesis of the research is approved. This means that changes in the rate of customer orientation, customer satisfaction has resulted in changes to the positive (increasing) sails. This means that the increase in customer orientation and increase customer satisfaction, and vice versa with positive tests, Pearson and Spearman coefficients, due to the increase of this relationship.

Sub hypotheses 1-5:

Between customer loyalty to customer relationship management and customer satisfaction in between buyers of audio and video products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

type relate	Relate	Number	Significance (p value)	The correlation coefficient	Statistics of solidarity
Direct	Yes	201	<0/001**	0/500	Pearson
Direct	yes	201	<0/001**	0/492	Spearman

Based on the results of the correlation test, Pearson correlation coefficient equal to 0/500 and Spearman correlation coefficients equal to 0/492, which is indicative of the customer loyalty to customer relationship management and customer satisfaction in consumer audio and video products Samsung in Kerman , there is a significant relationship(p<0/05) Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the relationship between these two variables is direct. Therefore, the first main hypothesis of the research is approved. This means that changes in the rate of customer loyalty to customer relationship management, customer satisfaction has resulted in changes to the positive (increasing) sails. This means that the increase in customer loyalty to customer relationship management and increase customer satisfaction, and vice versa with positive tests, Pearson and Spearman coefficients, due to the increase of this relationship.

Sub hypotheses 2-1:

Between product quality and customer value acceptable in between buyers of audio and video products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

type relate	Relate	Number	Significance (p value)	The correlation coefficient	Statistics of solidarity
Direct	Yes	201	<0/001**	0/749	Pearson
Direct	yes	201	<0/001**	0/739	Spearman

Based on the results of the correlation test, Pearson correlation coefficient equal to 0/749 and Spearman correlation coefficients equal to 0/739, which is indicative of the product quality and customer value acceptable in consumer audio and video products Samsung in Kerman , there is a significant relationship($p<0/05$) Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the relationship between these two variables is direct. Therefore, the first main hypothesis of the research is approved. This means that changes in the rate of product quality, customer value acceptable has resulted in changes to the positive (increasing) sails. This means that the increase in product quality and increase customer value acceptable, and vice versa with positive tests, Pearson and Spearman coefficients, due to the increase of this relationship.

Sub hypotheses 2-2:

Between service quality and customer value acceptable in between buyers of audio and video products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

type relate	Relate	Number	Significance (p value)	The correlation coefficient	Statistics of solidarity
Direct	Yes	201	<0/001**	0/753	Pearson
Direct	yes	201	<0/001**	0/697	Spearman

Based on the results of the correlation test, Pearson correlation coefficient equal to 0/753 and Spearman correlation coefficients equal to 0/697, which is indicative of the service quality and customer value acceptable in consumer audio and video products Samsung in Kerman, there is a significant relationship ($p<0/05$) Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the relationship between these two variables is direct. Therefore, the first main hypothesis of the research is approved. This means that changes in the rate of service quality, customer value acceptable has resulted in changes to the positive (increasing) sails. This means that the increase in service quality and increase customer value acceptable and vice versa with positive tests, Pearson and Spearman coefficients, due to the increase of this relationship.

Sub hypotheses 2-3:

Between The quality of the relationship between customer and supplier and customer value acceptable in between buyers of audio and video products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

type relate	Relate	Number	Significance (p value)	The correlation coefficient	Statistics of solidarity
Direct	Yes	201	<0/001**	0/797	Pearson
Direct	yes	201	<0/001**	0/763	Spearman

Based on the results of the correlation test, Pearson correlation coefficient equal to 0/797 and Spearman correlation coefficients equal to 0/763, which is indicative of the of the relationship between customer and supplier and customer value acceptable in consumer audio and video products Samsung in Kerman , there is a significant relationship($p<0/05$) Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the relationship between these two variables is direct. Therefore, the first main hypothesis of the research is approved. This means that changes in the rate of of the relationship between customer and supplier, customer value acceptable has resulted in changes to the positive (increasing) sails. This means that the increase in of the relationship between customer and supplier and increase customer value acceptable, and vice versa with positive tests, Pearson and Spearman coefficients, due to the increase of this relationship.

Sub hypotheses 2-4:

Between the image and customer value acceptable in between buyers of audio and video products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

type relate	Relate	Number	Significance (p value)	The correlation coefficient	Statistics of solidarity
Direct	Yes	201	<0/001**	0/560	Pearson
Direct	Yes	201	<0/001**	0/548	Spearman

Based on the results of the correlation test, Pearson correlation coefficient equal to 0/560 and Spearman correlation coefficients equal to 0/548, which is indicative of the image and customer value acceptable in consumer audio and video products Samsung in Kerman , there is a significant relationship($p<0/05$) Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the relationship between these two variables is direct. Therefore, the first main hypothesis of the research is approved. This means that changes in the rate of image, customer value acceptable has resulted in changes to the positive (increasing) sails. This means that the increase in image and increase customer value acceptable , and vice versa with positive tests, Pearson and Spearman coefficients, due to the increase of this relationship.

Sub hypotheses 2-5:

Between the price and customer value acceptable in between buyers of audio and video products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

type relate	Relate	Number	Significance (p value)	The correlation coefficient	Statistics of solidarity
Direct	Yes	201	<0/001**	0/574	Pearson
Direct	yes	201	<0/001**	0/545	Spearman

Based on the results of the correlation test, Pearson correlation coefficient equal to 0/574 and Spearman correlation coefficients equal to 0/545, which is indicative of the price and customer value acceptable in consumer audio and video products Samsung in Kerman , there is a significant relationship($p < 0/05$) Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the relationship between these two variables is direct. Therefore, the first main hypothesis of the research is approved. This means that changes in the rate of price, customer value acceptable has resulted in changes to the positive (increasing) sails. This means that the increase in price and increase customer value acceptable , and vice versa with positive tests, Pearson and Spearman coefficients, due to the increase of this relationship.

Sub hypotheses 1-3:

Between the identification of customer needs and customer value acceptable in between buyers of audio and video products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

type relate	Relate	Number	Significance (p value)	The correlation coefficient	Statistics of solidarity
Direct	Yes	201	<0/001**	0/687	Pearson
Direct	yes	201	<0/001**	0/659	Spearman

Based on the results of the correlation test, Pearson correlation coefficient equal to 0/687 and Spearman correlation coefficients equal to 0/659, which is indicative of the identification of customer needs and customer value acceptable in consumer audio and video products Samsung in Kerman , there is a significant relationship($p < 0/05$) Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the relationship between these two variables is direct. Therefore, the first main hypothesis of the research is approved. This means that changes in the rate of identification of customer needs, customer value acceptable has resulted in changes to the positive (increasing) sails. This means that the increase in identification of customer needs and increase customer value acceptable , and vice versa with positive tests, Pearson and Spearman coefficients, due to the increase of this relationship.

Sub hypotheses 2-3:

Between customer understanding and customer value acceptable in between buyers of audio and video products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

type relate	Relate	Number	Significance (p value)	The correlation coefficient	Statistics of solidarity
Direct	Yes	201	<0/001**	0/760	Pearson
Direct	yes	201	<0/001**	0/749	Spearman

Based on the results of the correlation test, Pearson correlation coefficient equal to 0/760 and Spearman correlation coefficients equal to 0/749, which is indicative of the customer understanding and customer value acceptable in consumer audio and video products Samsung in Kerman , there is a significant relationship($p < 0/05$) Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the relationship between these two variables is direct. Therefore, the first main hypothesis of the research is approved. This means that changes in the rate of customer understanding, customer value acceptable has resulted in changes to the positive (increasing) sails. This means that the increase in customer understanding and increase customer value acceptable and vice versa with positive tests, Pearson and Spearman coefficients, due to the increase of this relationship.

Sub hypotheses 3-3:

Between the flexible of services and customer value acceptable in between buyers of audio and video products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

type relate	Relate	Number	Significance (p value)	The correlation coefficient	Statistics of solidarity
Direct	Yes	201	<0/001**	0/744	Pearson
Direct	yes	201	<0/001**	0/727	Spearman

Based on the results of the correlation test, Pearson correlation coefficient equal to 0/744 and Spearman correlation coefficients equal to 0/727, which is indicative of the flexible of services and customer value acceptable in consumer audio and video products Samsung in Kerman, there is a significant relationship($p < 0/05$) Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the relationship between these two variables is direct. Therefore, the first main hypothesis of the research is approved. This means that changes in the rate of flexible of services, customer value acceptable has resulted in changes to the positive (increasing) sails. This means that the increase in flexible of services and increase customer value acceptable , and vice versa with positive tests, Pearson and Spearman coefficients, due to the increase of this relationship.

Sub hypotheses 3-4:

Between customer orientation and customer value acceptable in between buyers of audio and video products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

type relate	Relate	Number	Significance (p value)	The correlation coefficient	Statistics of solidarity
Direct	Yes	201	<0/001**	0/646	Pearson
Direct	yes	201	<0/001**	0/598	Spearman

Based on the results of the correlation test, Pearson correlation coefficient equal to 0/646 and Spearman correlation coefficients equal to 0/598, which is indicative of the customer orientation and customer value acceptable in consumer audio and video products Samsung in Kerman , there is a significant relationship($p < 0/05$) Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the relationship between these two variables is direct. Therefore, the first main hypothesis of the research is approved. This means that changes in the rate of customer orientation, customer value acceptable has resulted in changes to the positive (increasing) sails. This means that the increase in customer orientation and increase customer value acceptable , and vice versa with positive tests, Pearson and Spearman coefficients, due to the increase of this relationship.

Sub hypotheses 3-5:

Between customer loyalty to customer relationship management and customer value acceptable in between buyers of audio and video products in the town of Kerman there is a relationship.

type relate	Relate	Number	Significance (p value)	The correlation coefficient	Statistics of solidarity
Direct	Yes	201	<0/001**	0/705	Pearson
Direct	yes	201	<0/001**	0/689	Spearman

Based on the results of the correlation test, Pearson correlation coefficient equal to 0/705 and Spearman correlation coefficients equal to 0/689, which is indicative of the customer loyalty to customer relationship management and customer value acceptable in consumer audio and video products Samsung in Kerman, there is a significant relationship ($p < 0/05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the relationship between these two variables is direct. Therefore, the first main hypothesis of the research is approved. This means that changes in the rate of customer loyalty to customer relationship management, customer value acceptable has resulted in changes to the positive (increasing) sails. This means that the increase in customer loyalty to customer relationship management and increase customer value acceptable, and vice versa with positive tests, Pearson and Spearman coefficients, due to the increase of this relationship.

Discussion:

1 - The results indicate that it is the customer relationship management and customer satisfaction among buyers audio products Samsung in Kerman. There is a significant relationship. Given that, through the implementation of customer relationship management components, including customers, understanding customers, service flexibility, customer orientation, customer loyalty and customer relationship management, customer satisfaction can be audio and video products the enhanced performance and improved sales and customer relationship management, so the hypothesis is confirmed.

2 - The results of the study showed that between customer satisfaction and customer value among buyers in Kerman Samsung audio and video products, there is a significant relationship. Given that the implementation of the components of customer satisfaction, including product quality, price, quality, customer and supplier relationship quality, price, image, audio and video products that customers can be an acceptable value, and the sale of products promoted and improve customer satisfaction, so the hypothesis is confirmed.

3 - The results of study showed that the acceptable value of customer relationship management clients, the buyers, audio and video products Samsung in Kerman, there is a significant relationship. Due to the fact that through the implementation of customer relationship

management components, including: understanding the needs of our customers, understanding customers, service flexibility, customer orientation, customer loyalty and customer relationship management, customer satisfaction can be audio and enhanced video performance and improve sales and customer relationship management, so the hypothesis is confirmed.

4 - The results of the study showed that the level of understanding of customers' needs and satisfaction of customers, there is a significant relationship. Since job design is such that the talents and skills of staff are well used and staff responsibilities are adequate to determine the best way of doing things they also considered to success and is greatly appreciated they are given the opportunity to progress so employees try to better understand their customers' needs in a proper understanding of this result is increased customer satisfaction was clearer., So the hypothesis is confirmed.

5 - The results showed a significant correlation between the degree of understanding customers and satisfying customers there. Because understanding customer needs and understand customers or vendors relevant staff makes everything so we can build trust between the people is stronger than the trust will be greater customer satisfaction. So the hypothesis is confirmed.

6 - The results showed a significant correlation between the degree of flexibility, service and customer satisfaction there. The diversity of services, as well as greater flexibility in providing services for corporate customers. As a result, the value of the goods the customer goes up. And greater customer confidence that their products will provide more diverse services that will increase customer satisfaction. So the hypothesis is confirmed.

7 - The results showed a significant relationship between customer orientation and customer satisfaction there. Since each customer orientation, a company will increase customer satisfaction. So the hypothesis is confirmed.

8 - Results of the study showed that the level of customer loyalty, customer relationship management, customer satisfaction, there is a significant relationship. The higher the degree of customer loyalty, customer relationship management will increase relative to the increase in customer relationship management. It is a component that will increase customer satisfaction, and this relationship can be established to the contrary. So the hypothesis is confirmed.

9 - The results showed an acceptable level of product quality and customer value, there is a significant relationship. The quality of a product rises, thus increasing the value of this product will. As can be seen in all of human society, from the perspective of product popularity and more value to users is a high quality product that. Thus increasing product quality, increase customer value perspective., So the hypothesis is confirmed.

10 - Results showed an acceptable level of service quality and customer value, there is a significant relationship. Whatever the quality of a product will increase the value of the product should also result in increased. Because when a product tailored service. Such as after-sales services and guarantees or warranties have a person to buy the product than the buyer is relieved, relieved of the customer's point of view because of the high value of the product. After high service quality to increase customer value is acceptable., So the hypothesis is confirmed.

11 - Results of the study showed a relationship between customer and supplier quality acceptable to the customer, there is a significant relationship. It is obvious that the higher the quality of the customer relationship and supplier of each product, the better its value is higher than the product from the customer perspective. So the hypothesis is confirmed.

12 - The results showed the effectiveness and value acceptable to the customer, there is a significant relationship. The Yhtry image of a brand and a product of a society is common to find that commodity more popular in the community of users it has. The popularity of consumers goods, high value that represents the views of its customers. So the hypothesis is confirmed.

13 - Results of the study showed that the rates of price and value acceptable to the customer, there is significant correlation between the price of a commodity is of high value. And between individuals in a society, a product that has a high price must also be of high value to increase the price of a product increases customer value is therefore plausible hypothesis is confirmed.

14 - Results showed an acceptable level of understanding customer needs, customer value, there is a significant relationship. Since, understanding customer needs, customer satisfaction of the product will cause. The result is greater customer satisfaction and product value to the customer of the product rises. The overall result can be expressed in this way increasing the acceptable that increase customer recognition of the customer. So the hypothesis is confirmed.

15 - Results showed an acceptable level of mutual understanding customers and customer value, there is a significant relationship. The increased understanding of customers by retailers to increase customer value perspective., So the hypothesis is confirmed.

16 - Results showed an acceptable level of flexibility and value customer service, there is a significant relationship. The variety of services to clients as well as providing a greater flexibility. As a result, the value of the goods, the customer and consumer confidence rises more than good will by offering a variety of services. This increases customer value will be accepted. So the hypothesis is confirmed.

17 - Results showed acceptable rates between customer orientation and customer value, there is a significant relationship. Since the company will increase customer orientation, improved customer satisfaction and therefore increase the value of the customer's perspective. So the hypothesis is confirmed.

18 - Results of the study showed that the level of customer loyalty, customer relationship management and value, there is a significant relationship. Higher the degree of customer loyalty, customer relationship management, customer relationship management to increase constituents is increased. It also enhances the

customer will value this relationship can be established to the contrary., So the hypothesis is confirmed.

Research proposal:

Given that, and customer relationship management customer satisfaction customer with acceptable values, there is a significant relationship, the following recommendations to companies, organizations and researchers to strengthen their customer satisfaction are offered.

In order to enhance customer satisfaction:

1 - Using the approach ((Communication Management)) by corporate leaders that represent the importance of communication open and honest leader, with others, which makes identifying organizational talent and success in maintaining customer satisfaction.

2 - Use ((understanding customer needs)) to identify the customer needs and meet all these requirements and to enhance customer satisfaction and increase their confidence in the company.

3 - the application of confidence-and modes of approach ((trust-based management)), the background of customer satisfaction and therefore cause actual actions in order to manage the customer relationship.

4 - approach ((client-centered)) with features such as quality of service and quality of products in order to attract customers satisfaction.

In order to enhance customer value acceptable:

1 - Create a ((customer relationship management)), the willingness to accept more responsibility and a willingness to accept change and environmental changes.

2 - Using the approach ((flexibility to provide services)), which can explain the relationship between customer and supplier quality product with value added and thus enhance the customer.

3 - (price) with a strong customer relationship management and increase the product quality, reasonable prices, it can increase its value to the customer.

References

1.Aker. David, Strategic Market Management. 2nd edition, Trans: Safarizadeh. Hossein, Khademi. Mehdi, Farhangi. Ali Akbar, Tehran: Pouya, 2007.

2.Amiri. Yaser, study the quality of services of consumer relationship management and codification of optimal CRM plans in banking system through TOPSIS technique: case study: Shiraz Tejarat bank branches. Scientific-

Sanandaj, 4th year, no. 10, 2009.

3.Hagh gooei. Mojgan, Relationship marketing and consumer relationship management. Executive management research, 9th year, 82, 2-64, 2010

4. Khodadad hosseinin. Seyyed hamid, Asgharpour faz. Alireza, and Azizi. shahryar, Identification and prioritization of the effective factors on satisfaction of the consumers of Iran-khodro motorcars by using the model of hierarchial analysis process. Quarterly of management messages, 7 and 74, 8-47, 2004

5.Khosravi. Rahman, Codification and study the effective factors of consumers relationship management performance. M.A thesis statement, Islamic Azad University Of Qheshm, 2011

6.Divandari. Ali,& Delkhah. Khalil, Planning a model for evaluating cunsomers satisfaction in banking industry and evaluating the satisfaction of Mellat bank consumers based on this model. Quarterly of business researches, 223, 37-185,2005

7.Zegerdi. Seyyed Hesamadin, Identifying the effective factors of CRM fulfillment in services industry(case study: hotel industry of Iran). International conference of CRM, Tarbiat- Moddares university, 2007

8.Soltani. Hossein, Evaluating the relationship between consumer expectancy and performance of consumers relationship management in Madiran company(exclusive representative of LG monitors). First international conference of marketing management, 2006

9.Seyyed Javadeyn. Seyyed Reza, & Yousefi. Pouryia, Determining the effective factors on loyalty of consumers of IRAN Saderat Development bank by using CRM implications . Monthly review of business studies, 49, 18-34, 2006

10.Sharbatoghli.Ahmad, Ekhlasi. Amir, designing a model for evaluating consumers satisfaction in developing banking industry and evaluating consumers satisfaction in mining and industry bank based on this model. Quarterly of management knowledge(1995), 81, 21-57, 2008

11.Tahmasbi Ashtiani. Mahdyieh, and Norouzi. Ali, True relationship marketing. Tadbir44, 38-184, 2007

12. Ghafari Ashtiani. Peyman, Overlapping relationship marketing and consumers relationship management. Tadbir, 57, 54-181, 2007
13. Feyz. Davood, & Molazadeh. Ebrahim, Studying the effective factors of consumers satisfaction in Mehr finance and credit institution by using Cano model. Journal of human sciences department of Semnan university, 140, 21-123, 2008
14. Feyzi. Kamran, Kazazi. Abolfazl, and Khalili shojaei. Vahab, Consumers relationship management and consumers satisfaction based on services quality model (serkoal), in Parsian business electronic company. Quarterly of management studies, 131, 57-106
15. Katler. Philip, and Armestrang. Garry, Marketing rules. Trans: Parsian. Ali, Tehran: Adabestan, 9th edition, (1999), 2011
16. Moradi. Hasan, planning CRM strategies. M.A thesis statement, Pyame- Noor university of Karaj, 2008
17. Nayeb zadeh. Shahnaz, Value from consumers viewpionts. Tehran: Sharif university, 2006
18. Vakili fard. Hamidreza, Maran joori. Mehdi, and Alikhani. Razyieh, understanding CRM. Accountant Journal, 204, 69-75
19. Research and development unit, department of commerce, conference on e- money, (2004)
- 20- Allerd , K. ,and Addams ,C.J. (2000).”**Customer relationship management**” Mc Graw Hill Trade.
- 21- Aydin, S., Ozer, G., Arasil, O.(2005).”**Customer loyalty and the effect of switching costs as a moderator variable**”. Marketing Intelligence & Planning ,Vol.23,No.1,pp 89-103.
- 22- Beerli A. Martin J.D. Quintana A. (2004).”**A model of eustomer loyalty in the retail banking market**”.European Journal of marketing. Vol ,38,No,1/2,pp.253-275.
- 23- Brown , S.A. (2000). ”**Customer Relationship Management: A strategic imperative in the world of e-business**”. John wiley & Sons.
- 24- Bruhn and Grund.(2000).”**Theory ,development and implementation of national customer satisfaction indices.(SWICS)**”.Total Quality Management ,Vol,11,No,7,pp:1017-1028.
- 25- Hoisington ,S. And Naumann , E. (2003).”**The loyalty Elophant** “.Quality Progress , February ,pp 33-41.
- 26- Kassanoff , B. (2000). “ **Build loyalty into your e-Business, in proceedings of DCI customer relationship management confereuce**”.Boston,MA:june,27-29.
- 27- Molina , A and Martin-Consuegra , D and Esteban , A . (2007) “**Relational benefits and customer satisfaction in retail banking** “. International Journal of Bank Marketing ,Vol,25,No,4,pp.253-271.
- 28- Paul , D. Berger and nada I.Nasr.(2000).”**Customer lifetime value marketing models and applications**”. Journal Of Interactive Marketing ,Vol,23,No,5,pp.27-30.
- 29- Pratten , K. (2004) .” **Customer satisfaction and waiting staff** “. International of Contemporary Hospitality management , Vol,16,No,4,pp.385-388.
- 30- Redondo and Fierro. (2005). “**moderating effect of type of product exchanged in long term orientation of firm supplier relationships** “. Journal of Product And Brand management ,424-437.
- 31- Russell , P. and winer , J.S. (2001). “**Product management**”. 3rd edition, Mc Graw Hill.
- 32- Sapinet consulting company ,Creating value through CRM. White paper (2004) [online], <http://WWW.sapinet.com/pdfs/industry viewpoint . CRM.fs.pdf>.
- 33- Theorandic , R.L. (2002). “**Customer relationship management (CRM) in financial services** “.European management Journal ,Vol,18 ,No,3,pp.312-327.
- 34- Wang , A. (2004). “**An integrated frame work for customer value and customer relationship management** “.Managing Service Quality , 169-182.
- 35- Leo Y.M. Sin , Alan C.B. Tse and Frederick H.k. Yim. (2005). “**CRM : conceptualization and scale development** “. , vol,39, No11/12 ,1264-1290.